

Social media and its impact during the Covid-19

¹Lee Zi Shin, ²Sun Li Ting, ³Dr. Logenthini Mariappan

^{1,2,3} Raffles University, Malaysia

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7745015>

Published Date: 17-March-2023

Abstract: The primary object of this study is to survey the impact of social media on Covid-19. Therefore, a lot of research has been conducted to determine how social media is being used during the Covid-19 pandemic. Since social media have become the only means of connecting people throughout the world during the Covid-19 pandemic, this paper explores the way social media are affecting people and how this affects the Covid-19 pandemic. To that end, structured questionnaires were distributed to 256 participants. In a questionnaire, the message of respondents has been included, along with their motivational and burden factors, which are evident in their use of social media during the Covid-19 pandemic. People experience emotional problems due to the Covid-19 pandemic and are forced to look after their dependents, while some have the chance to increase their income with social media use. This research contributed to our present understanding of the public's reactions to social media during the Covid-19 pandemic. Our study found that people used social media a lot during the Covid-19 pandemic. Therefore, we can minimize the difficulties they will encounter on social media, helping them use it easily.

Keywords: Social media, Covid-19 pandemic, Emotional, Public.

1. INTRODUCTION

Before this Covid-19, we had not had an uncontrolled pandemic, even though it was swine flu (H1N1) (Cleveland Clinic, n.d.) noted that we still have a method to control it, and that is everyone getting vaccinated annually. Next, the research found that the first Covid-19 was occurrence in Wuhan City, Hubei Province, China, on 12th December 2019 (Elengoe, 2020). At that time, we were still safe in Malaysia since there was no Covid-19 infection, but those who are worried about being infected started wearing masks. Our government has also acted in the form of a Movement Control Order (MCO) since the situation has worsened.

MCO continues for a long time due to this COVID-19 pandemic and because of the widespread of the contagious virus, people have already started to work from home (WFH) and study at home through social media to avoid falling behind. Consequently, everyone is using social media more often, including old people, during this Covid-19 pandemic. It can be said that we can get the latest information about this pandemic through social media, so we can easily get fake news about Covid-19. As everyone can post whatever they want on social media, we will face misunderstandings from influencers, which can negatively impact our lives. Tabong and Segtub (2021) noted found that the changes in the misunderstanding of Covid-19, initially people believed black people were immune to Covid-19. Also, people believe that old people will get a severe disease of the contagious virus, and people have already started to work from home (WFH) and study at home through social media to avoid falling behind. Consequently, everyone is using social media more often, including old people, during this Covid-19 pandemic. It can be said that we can get the latest information about this pandemic through social media, so we can easily get fake news about Covid-19. As everyone can post whatever they want on social media, we will face misunderstandings from influencers, which can negatively impact our lives. Tabong and Segtub (2021) noted found that the changes in the misunderstanding of Covid-19, initially people believed black people were immune to Covid-19. Also, people believe that old people will get severe diseases, and this misunderstanding makes the younger generation feel safe. In the end, people think that the hot weather in Africa stopped the Covid-19 pandemic, but also think that Covid-19 was a biological weapon only against the economics of the world.

Concurrently we can see how social media is becoming a necessity during this Covid-19 pandemic. In our experience, the reason is that people discover the convenience and significance of social media, so they use social media frequently. Thus, this study has taken into consideration all those outputs and came out with an understanding to survey the public of the impact.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Social media had an impact during COVID-19 because more and more people are using social media to do home-based business and academic research. The research shows that the increased level of work involved is related to communicating at work through social media, as well as the sense of support from public and work resources (Oksa, Kaakinen, Savela, Hakanen, & Oksanen, 2021). The steady growth helped the company stay on track during the Covid-19 pandemic with less burden in all aspects. Next, TikTok (689 million users) and QQ (617 million users) became the most famous social media websites. These websites can share any document and make new friends (Madziva, Nachipo, Masuka, Chitungo, Murewanhema, Phiri, & Dzinamarira, 2022). In this case, we can know that social media can give us a lot of emotions, and we can also earn money through social media since lots of people are using this kind of application.

Motivational and emotional aspects

In the era of social media, fear of Coronavirus spreads more quickly than the virus itself (Muwahed, 2020, as cited in Ahmad & Murad, 2020). Everyone sees information about Covid-19 on social media during the pandemic, so some people use this opportunity to share fake news to get concern from the public and let people share the information with others. This easily makes the public anxious when they see the news as they do not know what is true. Other than that, most Covid-19 patients had severe posttraumatic stress symptoms related to the illness before being discharged, and these symptoms may have adverse effects like decreased quality of life and reduced productivity (Bo, Li, Yang, Wang, Zhang, Cheung, Wu, & Xiang, 2020). Therefore, emotional feelings can also be solved through social media as a lot of experts have been on social media too.

Income and dependent burden

A huge real income shock would be experienced by households with low levels of education and high reliance on labor income severely limiting their ability to afford food (Arndt, Davies, Gabriel, Harris, Makrelov, Robinson, Levy, Simbanegavi, Seventer, & Anderson, 2020). As a result of the Covid-19 pandemic, the unemployment rate was also higher. A child may also be a dependent burden if his or her sister or parent is injured and has to be looked after. They need to try to find new work through social media. In this case, they need to learn how to start their business otherwise they will lose their source of finance.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study used a quantitative research design. The survey questionnaire was used, and the samples were chosen randomly. A total of 256 sample participants responded to the questionnaire and the response was recorded. The total score with the percentage was presented in the findings of the study.

4. RESEARCH FINDINGS

Figure 1: The age of the public.

In the first question of the perception part where the respondents were asked their age almost 222 people responded which is about 86.7% responded they are between 15-21 years. Almost 26 of the people respond they are between 22-28 years. Also, 5 people responded they are 36 years and above which is 2%, and 3 people responded they were between 29-35 years. which was 1.2%.

Figure 2: The gender of the public.

In the second question of the perception part where the respondents were asked about gender almost 189 people responded which is about 73.8% responded they were female, and the rest 26.2% the people were male.

Figure 3: The country in public life.

In the third question of the perception part where the respondents were asked about the country, they live 254 people responded which is about 99.2% responded they were Malaysian and the rest 0.8% the people were Singaporean, were just 2 persons.

Figure 4: The monthly household income of the public.

In the fourth question of the perception part where the respondents were asked about the monthly household income, almost 107 people responded which is about 41.8% responded their household income is below RM2500. Almost 59 of the people responded their household income is between RM2501-RM5500. Also, 48 people responded their household income was between RM501-RM8000 which was 18.8% and 42 people responded their household income was RM8001 and above which was 16.4%.

Figure 5: The number depends on the public in the house.

In the fifth question of the perception part where the respondents were asked about the number of dependents in the house, almost 96 people responded which is about 37.5% responded their number of dependents in the house was between 3-4. Almost 87 of the people responded their number of dependents in the house was 5 and above. Also, 51 people responded their number dependent in the house was between 1-2 which was 19.9% and 22 people responded their number dependent in the house was zero which was 8.6%.

Figure 6

In the sixth question of the perception part where the respondents were asked about the language used in social media, 176 people responded which is about 68.8% responded they used Chinese, and 77 people responded which was about 30.1% responded they used English. Also, 2 persons responded they used Malay which was 0.8%. Lastly, one person had written down in others that he/she used Japanese.

Figure 7: The education level of the public.

In the seventh question of the perception part where the respondents were asked on the education level, 158 people responded which is about 61.7% responded they had a university education level and 92 people responded about 35.9% responded they had a secondary education level. Lastly, the rest of the people had written down their answers in others which are primary, SPM, college, kindergarten, diploma, and pre-university all got 0.4% which was 1 person for each.

Figure 8: Has the public been infected by Covid-19 before?

In the eighth question of the perception part where the respondents were asked on have u been a COVID-19 patient before, almost 165 people responded which is about 64.5% responded they had been a Covid-19 patient before, and the rest of 35.5% people they had not been a Covid-19 patient before?

Figure 9: Public's frequency of using social media in a day.

In the ninth question of the perception part where the respondents were asked about the frequency of using social media in a day almost 159 people responded which is about 62.1% responded their frequency of it was 1-8 hours. Almost 67 of the people responded their frequency of it was 9-14 hours. Also, 26 people responded their frequency of it was more than 14 hours which was 10.2% and 4 people responded their frequency of it was below 1 hour which was 1.6%.

Figure 10: Has the public been affected emotionally or mentally during covid 19?

In the tenth question of the perception part where the respondents were asked on have u been affected emotionally or mentally during covid 19, almost 131 of peoples responded which was about 51.2% responded they had been affected emotionally or mentally during covid 19 and the rest of 48.8% people they had not been affected emotionally or mentally during covid 19.

Part B: Motivational and emotional aspects

The internet connection in my country is good.

256 jawaban

Figure 1: Is the internet connection in a public country nice?

In the first question of the Motivational and emotional aspect part where the respondents were asked on the internet connection in my country was good almost 132 people responded was about 51.6% responded Neutral. Almost 53 respondents agreed that the internet connection in their country was good. Also, 55 responded disagree which is 21.5% and 3 responded strongly agree which was 1.2%. Lastly, the rest of the 5.1% the people responded strongly disagree.

I have plenty of time during Covid-19 pandemic.

256 jawaban

Figure 2: Public got plenty of time during the Covid-19 pandemic.

In the second question of the Motivational and emotional aspect part where the respondents were asked, I had plenty of time during the Covid-19 pandemic almost 67 people responded was about 26.2% responded Neutral. Almost 119 people who responded agreed that they had plenty of time during the Covid-19 pandemic. Also, 17 people responded to disagree which was 6.6% and 41 people responded strongly agree which was 16%. Lastly, the rest of the 12% of people responded strongly disagree.

I feel stress during Covid-19 pandemic.

256 jawapan

Figure 3: Public felt stress during the Covid-19 pandemic.

In the third question of the Motivational and emotional aspect part where the respondents were asked, I felt stress during the Covid-19 pandemic almost 109 people responded about 42.6% responded Neutral. Almost 67 of the people who responded agreed that they felt stress during the Covid-19 pandemic. Also, 46 people responded disagree which was 18% and 18 people responded strongly agree which was 7%. Lastly, the rest of the 6.3% of people responded strongly disagree.

I feel less motivated during Covid-19 pandemic.

256 jawapan

Figure 4: Public felt less motivated during the Covid-19 pandemic.

In the fourth question of the Motivational and emotional aspect part where the respondents were asked, I felt less motivated during the Covid-19 pandemic almost 65 people responded was about 25.4% responded Neutral. Almost 112 of the people who responded agreed that they felt less motivated during the Covid-19 pandemic. Also, 28 people responded to disagree which was 10.9% and 38 people responded strongly agree which was 14.8%. Lastly, the rest of the 5.1% the people responded strongly disagree.

I miss the working /studying environments during Covid-19 pandemic.

256 jawapan

Figure 5: Public missed the working /studying environments during the Covid-19 pandemic.

In the fifth question of the Motivational and emotional aspect part where the respondents were asked on, I missed the working /studying environments during the Covid-19 pandemic almost 80 people responded was about 31.3% responded Neutral. Almost 79 of the people who responded agreed that they missed the working /studying environments during the Covid-19 pandemic. Also, 37 people responded to disagree which was 14.5% and 40 people responded strongly agree which was 15.6%. Lastly, the rest of the 7.8% of people responded strongly disagree.

Depression due to drop to economic states.

256 jawapan

Figure 6: Public felt depressed due to a drop in economic status.

In the sixth question of the Motivational and emotional aspect, the part where the respondents were asked about Depression due to a drop in economic status almost 105 people responded which was about 41% responded Neutral. Almost 90 of the people who responded agreed that they depression due to a drain on economic states. Also, 20 people responded to disagree which was 7.8% and 29 people responded strongly agree which was 11.3%. Lastly, the rest of the 4.7% of people responded strongly disagree.

Part C: Income and dependent burden

The income is sufficient for me during Covid-19 pandemic.

256 responses

Figure 1: The income was sufficient for the public during the Covid-19 pandemic.

In the first question of the income and dependent burden, the part where the respondents were asked about income was sufficient for me during the Covid-19 pandemic almost 112 people responded was about 43.8% responded Neutral. Almost 71 of the people who responded agreed that their income was sufficient for them during the Covid-19 pandemic. Also, 50 people responded to disagree which was 19.5% and 14 people responded strongly agree which was 5.5%. Lastly, the rest of 3.5% of people responded strongly disagree.

Social media helped me to boost up my income during Covid-19 pandemic.
256 responses

Figure 2: social media helped the public to boost their income during the Covid-19 pandemic.

In the second question of the income and dependent burden part where the respondents were asked on social media helped to boost their income during the Covid-19 pandemic almost 111 people responded was about 43.4% responded Neutral. Almost 66 of the people who responded disagreed that social media helped them to boost their income during the Covid-19 pandemic. Also, 52 people responded to agree which was 20.3% and 20 people responded strongly disagree which was 7.8%. Lastly, the rest of 2.7% of people responded strongly agree.

I was difficult to get a job during Covid-19 pandemic.
254 responses

Figure 3: The public was difficulty getting a job during the Covid-19 pandemic.

In the third question of the income and dependent burden part where the respondents were asked, if it was difficult to get a job during the Covid-19 pandemic almost 117 people responded was about 46.1% responded Neutral. Almost 80 of the people who responded agreed that they were difficult to get a job during the Covid-19 pandemic. Also, 24 people responded to disagree which was 9.4% and 20 people responded strongly agree which was 7.9%. Lastly, the rest of the 5.1% of people responded strongly disagree.

I bought more thing through social media during Covid 19 pandemic.
256 responses

Figure 4: Public bought more things through social media during Covid 19.

In the fourth question of the income and dependent burden part where the respondents were asked, I bought more things through social media during Covid 19 almost 99 people responded which was about 38.7% responded agreed. Almost 73 people responded neutrally that they bought more things through social media during Covid 19. Also, 48 people responded strongly agree which was 18.8% and 30 people responded disagree which was 11.7%. Lastly, the rest of the 2.3% of people responded strongly disagree.

My quality of life decreased during Covid-19 pandemic .
256 responses

Figure 5: Public's quality of life decreased during the Covid-19 pandemic.

In the fifth question of the income and dependent burden part where the respondents were asked about, my quality of life decreased during the Covid-19 pandemic almost 93 people responded was about 36.3% responded Neutral. Almost 91 people who responded agreed that their quality of life decreased during the Covid-19 pandemic. Also, 41 people responded to disagree which was 16% and 23 people responded strongly agree which was 9%. Lastly, the rest of 3.1% of people responded strongly disagree.

I used social media for work during the Covid-19 pandemic and was positively impacted by it.
256 responses

Figure 6: Public used social media for work during the Covid-19 pandemic and was positively impacted by it.

In the sixth question of the income and dependent burden part where the respondents were asked, I used social media for work during the Covid-19 pandemic and was positively impacted by it almost 123 people responded which was about 48% responded Neutral. Almost 65 peoples responded agreed that they used social media for work during the Covid-19 pandemic and was positively impacted by it. Also, 42 people responded disagree which was 16.4%, strongly agree and strongly disagree got the same result which was 13 people answered for each answer.

The company I work for is on the verge of bankruptcy during Covid-19 pandemic.
256 responses

Figure 7: The company that the public worked for was on the verge of bankruptcy during the Covid-19 pandemic.

In the seventh question of the income and dependent burden part where the respondents were asked on the company that I work for was on the verge of bankruptcy during the Covid-19 pandemic almost 125 people responded was about 48.8% responded Neutral. Almost 60 people responded and disagreed that the company that they work for was on the verge of bankruptcy during the Covid-19 pandemic. Also, people responded strongly disagree which was 15.6% and 27 people responded to agree which was 10.5%. Lastly, the rest of the 1.6% of people responded strongly agree.

Expenses of electricity and utility increase during Covid 19 pandemic.
256 responses

Figure 8: Public's expenses for electricity and utility increased during Covid 19 pandemic.

In the eighth question of the income and dependent burden part where the respondents were asked about, expenses of electricity and utility increased during Covid 19 pandemic almost 126 people responded which was about 49.2% responded agreed. Almost 81 people responded neutrally that expenses of electricity and utility increased during Covid 19 pandemic. Also, 32 people responded strongly agree which was 12.5% and 10 people responded disagree which was 3.9%. Lastly, the rest of 2.7% of people responded strongly disagree.

Grab orders have significantly increased during Covid-19 pandemic.
256 responses

Figure 9: Public belief Grab orders significantly increased during the Covid-19 pandemic.

In the ninth question of the income and dependent burden part where the respondents were asked on, grab orders had significantly increased during the Covid-19 pandemic almost 103 people responded which was about 40.2% responded agreed. Almost 77 people responded strongly agree that grab orders had significantly increased during the Covid-19 pandemic. Also, 59 people responded neutrally which was 23% and 11 people responded disagree which was 4.3%. Lastly, the rest of the 2.3% of people responded strongly disagree.

Playing shares can earn more money during the COVID-19 pandemic.
253 responses

Figure 10: Public belief playing shares can earn more money during the COVID-19 pandemic.

In the tenth question of the income and dependent burden part where the respondents were asked on, playing shares can be earned more money during the COVID-19 pandemic almost 132 people responded was about 52.2% responded Neutral. Almost 67 people responded agreed that playing shares can be earned more money during the COVID-19 pandemic. Also, 30 people responded to disagree which was 11.9% and 14 people responded strongly agree which was 5.5%. Lastly, the rest of the 4% of people responded strongly disagree.

5. CONCLUSION

Due to the Covid-19 pandemic, we often utilize social media to connect with everyone. From our survey, we know that public motivation and burden were evident in their use of social media during the Covid-19 pandemic. The responses show that the public felt less motivated during the Covid-19 pandemic because they only can stay at home. Besides, social media bring us convenience we can buy more things through social media besides buying daily necessities, e also can grab food online without going out to contact people during this situation. As recommended, people can also wear masks, keep away from crowded places, keep their distance from people, and have self-quarantine. In conclusion, social media helps us a lot when the Covid-19 pandemic befalls, such as bringing us convenience and improving the market in social media.

REFERENCES

- [1] Cleveland Clinic. (n.d.). Swine flu (H1N1). <https://my.clevelandclinic.org/health/diseases/23928-swine-flu-h1n1>
- [2] Elengoe, A. (2020). Covid-19 outbreak in Malaysia. *Osong Public Health Res Perspect*, 11(3), 93–100. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7258884/>
- [3] Tabong, P.T.N & Segtub, M. (2021). *Misconceptions, misinformation and politics of COVID-19 on social media: A multi-level analysis in Ghana*. *Frontiers in Communication*. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fcomm.2021.613794/full>
- [4] Oksa, R., Kaakinen, M., Savela, N., Hakanen, J. J., & Oksanen, A. (2021). Professional social media usage and work engagement among professionals in Finland before and during the COVID-19 pandemic: Four-wave follow-up study. *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 23(6). <https://www.jmir.org/2021/6/e29036>
- [5] Madziva, R., Nachipo, B., Masuka, G., Chitungo, I., Murewanhema, G., Phiri, B., & Dzinamarira, T. (2022). The role of social media during the COVID-19 pandemic: Salvaging its 'power' for positive social behaviour change in Africa. *Health Promot Perspect*, 12(1), 22–27. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC9277293/>
- [6] Ahmad, A. R., & Murad, H. R. (2022). The impact of social media on panic during the COVID-19 pandemic in Iraqi Kurdistan: Online questionnaire study. *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 22(5). <https://www.jmir.org/2020/5/e19556#ref14>
- [7] Bo, H. X., Li, W., Yang, Y., Wang, Y., Zhang, Q., Cheung, T., Wu, X., & Xiang, Y. T. (2020). Posttraumatic stress symptoms and attitude toward crisis mental health services among clinically stable patients with COVID-19 in China. *Psychol Med*. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7200846/>
- [8] Arndt, C., Davies, R., Gabriel, S., Harris, L., Makrelov, K., Robinson, S., Levy, S., Simbanegavi, W., Seventer, D. V., & Anderson, L. (2020). Covid-19 lockdowns, income distribution, and food security: An analysis for South Africa. *Global Food Security*, 26. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S221191242030064X>